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Separation Workflow

Overall study design

Title of the study				Lipidomics Reporting Checklist - Example: Fibroblast HILIC-QQQ			
Document creation date		09/05/2024		Corresponding Email		Forename.Surname@gmail.com	
Principal investigator		Forename Surname		Is the workflow targeted or untargeted?		Targeted	
Institution		University XY		Clinical		No	

Lipid extraction

Extraction method	2-phase system	Were internal standards added prior extraction?	Yes
pH adjustment	None	Special conditions	-
2-phase system	Bligh&Dyer	Derivatization	-

Analytical platform

Ionization additives	Ammonium formate, Formic acid	Ion source	ESI
Number of separation dimensions	One dimension	MS Level	MS2
Separation type 1	LC	Mass window for precursor ion isolation (in Da total isolation window)	0.8
Separation mode 1 (liquid)	HILIC	Mass resolution for detected ion at MS2	Low resolution
Detector	Mass spectrometer	Resolution at MS2	Low
MS type	QQQ	Recording mode of raw data at MS2	Centroid mode
MS vendor	Mass Spec Company	Was/Were additional dimension/techniques used	No

Quality control

Blanks	Yes	Quality control	Yes
Type of Blanks	Extraction blank, Solvent blank, Internal standard blank	Type of QC sample	Sample pool

Method qualification and validation

Method validation	Yes	Precision	Yes
Lipid recovery	Yes	Accuracy	Yes
Dynamic quantification range	Yes	Guidelines followed	None
Limit of quantitation (LOQ)/Limit of detection (LOD)	Yes		

Reporting

Are reported raw data uploaded into repository?	Available on request	Raw data upload	No
Are metadata available?	Available on request	Additional comments	-

Sample Descriptions

Fibroblasts / Human / Cells

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage time (month)	1
Provided preanalytical information	Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Freeze-thaw cycles	1
Temperature handling original sample	Room temperature	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	15	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No
Storage temperature	-20 °C		

Lipid Class Descriptions

1) BMP[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	BMP	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3		
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes		
Identification level	Molecular species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interfece confirmed	Yes		
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	No		
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH4] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-		
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Homemade		
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Fragment name</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>FA1(+C3H6O2)</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Fragment name	FA1(+C3H6O2)		
Fragment name					
FA1(+C3H6O2)					
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Data manipulation	-		
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes		
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A		
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	Separation of isomeric PG and BMP verified with standards		
Check on:	Isomeric overlap				

1) BMP[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No						
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	Yes						
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Homemade						
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Internal standard</th> <th>Fragment(s)</th> <th>Endogenous subclass</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>BMP 14:0/14:0</td> <td>FA1(+C3H6O2)</td> <td>for all BMP</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	BMP 14:0/14:0	FA1(+C3H6O2)	for all BMP		
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass							
BMP 14:0/14:0	FA1(+C3H6O2)	for all BMP							
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No						
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-						
Type I isotope correction	Yes								

2) PG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PG	Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3		
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes		
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	Yes		
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	No		
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH4] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-		
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Homemade		
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Fragment name</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>-HG(PG,172+NH4)</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Fragment name	-HG(PG,172+NH4)		
Fragment name					
-HG(PG,172+NH4)					
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Data manipulation	-		
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes		
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A		
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	Separation of isomeric PG and BMP verified with standards		
Check on:	Isomeric overlap				

2) PG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No						
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	Yes						
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Homemade						
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Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass							
PG 14:0/14:0	-HG(PG,172+NH4) for all PG								
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No						
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-						
Type I isotope correction	Yes								